

O₂ Formation in Cold Environments

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Abstract

The diffusional dynamics of atomic oxygen in and on amorphous solid water (ASW) to form molecular oxygen is characterized. Reactive molecular dynamics simulations to study bond breaking and bond formation show that vibrational relaxation of the highly excited diatomic occurs on the 10 ns to 100 ns time scale. The relaxation process is highly nonexponential and can be characterized by a stretched exponential decay reminiscent of the dynamics of glasses. The stretched exponents range from $\beta = 0.15$ for relaxation on the surface to $\beta = 0.21$ for the dynamics in bulk. It is also found that coupling of the O₂ relaxation to the internal water modes occurs which speeds up the vibrational relaxation by a factor of 4. Extrapolation of the stretched exponential decay to 1 μ s yields a final vibrational quantum number $v = 2$ for O₂ ($X^3\Sigma_g^-$), consistent with experimental results from photolysis of SO₂ on ASW at 193 nm which find $v \leq 3$. Desorption energies of water from the surface range from 1.5 to 2.0 kcal/mol compared with 1.8 kcal/mol found from experiment, depending on whether the water molecules are flexible or not.

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Figure 1: Oxygen recombination in side amorphous solid water

1 Introduction

The mobility of atomic and molecular species on solid surfaces is a primary driver for surface-induced chemistry at low temperatures. It has been found from experiments^{1,2} and atomistic simulations^{3,4} that H and O atoms can diffuse on amorphous water surfaces down to low temperatures (~ 10 K). This is relevant for the possibility to form diatomic or larger molecules (such as O_2 , O_3 or CO_2) in laboratory experiments² and may also play a role for the conditions in interstellar space.⁵⁻⁷ If other atomic species than hydrogen (such as N, C, or O) are able to diffuse on cold surfaces, the range of molecules that can be formed by diffusion and aggregation is considerably expanded. Given the very long processing times (\sim years or longer) that are available in translucent, diffuse and dense molecular clouds,^{5,8} the accessible chemical space from such reaction pathways may be affected appreciably.

Molecular oxygen is an important tracer for characterizing the physical properties of star forming regions and molecular clouds and is implicated in various chemical processes leading to diverse chemical compositions in the interstellar space. Molecular oxygen in interstellar clouds was directly observed in the ρ Ophiuchi cloud using submillimeter wave spectroscopy.⁹ Understanding of the formation and ensuing concentration¹⁰ of O_2 is relevant for better characterizing the evolution of stellar clouds and their chemical composition.

In interstellar clouds, dust provides a suitable substrate for deposition and chemical synthesis of a variety of small molecules in a bottom-up fashion. Due to the low temperatures (10 K to 50 K),^{5,8} residence times are long despite the small barriers (~ 1 to 2 kcal/mol)^{11,12} for desorption and migration which also allows reactions to occur. In laboratory experiments with amorphous solid water as the substrate, deposition of oxygen (O) and O_2 leads to ozone formation at 10 K.^{13,14} These experiments suggest that using pure oxygen species, only two reactions are relevant: $O + O \rightarrow O_2$ and $O + O_2 \rightarrow O_3$.² In the experiments atomic oxygen ($O(^3P)$) was generated from dissociating O_2 through a microwave discharge and it

was verified that all participating species are in their ground electronic state. In modeling interstellar processes, the $O + O \rightarrow O_2$ channel is sometimes included⁵ and sometimes not.¹⁵ Another, and probably the predominant,^{16,17} O_2 -formation reaction is $O + OH \rightarrow O_2 + H$. A more exhaustive list of O_2 -formation reactions, including $O + OH \rightarrow O_2 + H$ in the gas phase¹⁸ or on the surface of grains,¹⁹ can be found in the KIDA database.²⁰

It has been previously shown by experiment and simulations that migration of atomic species, such as oxygen, in ASW is readily possible on the sub-microsecond time scale over distances of several ten Angstroms.^{2,4} Similarly, oxygen atom diffusion in Neon matrices at temperatures as low as 4 K has recently been established.²¹ Diffusing oxygen atoms have also been implicated in the formation of CO_2 through $O + CO \rightarrow CO_2$.²²⁻²⁴ This pathway for the formation of molecular species from adsorbates is generally known as the Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism²⁵

Figure 2: Two physical conditions in which O_2 formation is studied: panel A shows two oxygen atoms (red) trapped inside a cavity of the ASW (grey); in panel B shows the two on top of the water surface.

In laboratory experiments using amorphous solid water, formation of ground state $^3\Sigma_g^-$ (from $\text{OH} + \text{O}(^3\text{P})$ with $\Delta H = -68$ kJ/mol) and excited state $^1\Delta_g$ O_2 (from $\text{OH} + \text{O}(^3\text{P})$ with $\Delta H = 26$ kJ/mol) was found following electronic excitation of the ASW with 157 nm irradiation at 90 K.¹⁷ This process for O_2 formation follows a non-equilibrium route, involves higher electronic states and differs from the processes considered in temperature-programmed desorption experiments.² The study of SO_2 photolysis at 193 nm adsorbed on ASW yields $\text{O}_2(^3\Sigma_g^-)$ from recombination of $\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}(^3\text{P})$ with $\Delta H = -498$ kJ/mol.¹⁷ Furthermore, a model for formation of O_2 following electronic excitation of ice by fast ions, low-energy electrons, and UV photons at low temperatures was presented.²⁶ In this model trapped $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ is the principal species considered for formation of O_2 at low doses. This route for O_2 formation is also implicated in the atmospheres of the icy moons of Jupiter and in the rings of Saturn, where molecular oxygen has been detected as a result of the decomposition of ice by energetic ions and electrons or by UV photon-induced production from ice.

In the present work the dynamics of O_2 formation in and on amorphous solid water (ASW) from collision of two $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ is studied. The main questions considered are the possibility for formation and stabilization, the likely formation time scales, the vibrational relaxation of highly excited O_2 following recombination, the desorption of molecular oxygen following a Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism and the energy transfer between the energized molecule and the surrounding water matrix. After presenting the methods, atomic oxygen recombination within and on the surface of an ice grain is considered and analyzed. Then, the desorption dynamics from the oxygen is considered.

2 Methods

2.1 Molecular Dynamics Simulations

All reactive MD simulations are carried out using CHARMM²⁷ with MS-ARMD^{28–30} and the Leap Frog integrator with a time step of $\Delta t = 0.1$ fs. Such a short time step is required due to the high vibrational excitation upon Oxygen-Oxygen recombination and also in simulations with flexible water (vide infra). The simulation system is a cubic box with dimensions $(31 \text{ \AA})^3$ with periodic boundary conditions and the nonbonded cutoff is 14 \AA . The box size along the z -axis is elongated by 20 \AA to allow for surface desorption of the O and O₂ adsorbate. Initial velocities are drawn from a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution at 50 K. All simulations are initialized as follows: a minimization of 100 steps using the steepest descent method is followed by 10 ps heating, where the temperature is increased by 10 K every ps and then relaxed for the last 5 ps, and 50 ps equilibration dynamics with rescaling of the temperatures every 2.5 ps. Then, the following different types of simulations are considered: the (rigid) TIP3P³¹) or the (flexible) KKY^{32,33} water model are combined with either a reproducing kernel Hilbert space (RKHS) or a Morse representation of the reactive O–O potential (vide infra) to follow the recombination and relaxation dynamics.

Oxygen (O₂) formation from collision of two oxygen atoms is studied by using reactive MD which requires two potential energy surfaces, one for the unbound state (O+O), and a second one for bound O₂. MS-ARMD then handles the transition between the two states.²⁸ Only the state with the lowest energy is propagated in the simulations except for configurations for which the energy difference between the lowest and next higher-energy states is within ΔV for which mixing of the two (or multiple) states occurs. In those cases the total energy for each configuration \mathbf{x} is the weighted sum of the involved states:

$$V_{\text{MRMD}}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i(\mathbf{x}) V_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad (1)$$

where V_{MRMD} is the total energy surface, $w_i(\mathbf{x})$ is the weight of the i^{th} state with energy V_i . The weight

$$w_i(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{w_{i,0}(\mathbf{x})}{\sum_{j=1}^n w_{j,0}(\mathbf{x})} \quad (2)$$

is calculated by re-normalizing the raw weights $w_{i,0}$, using an exponential decay function of the energy difference between the minimum v_{min} and the i^{th} surface.

$$w_{i,0}(\mathbf{x}) = \exp\left(\frac{V_i(\mathbf{x}) - V_{\text{min}}(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta V}\right) \quad (3)$$

In this work two states are used for the dynamics: the unbound state, described by two isolated oxygen atoms which interact through nonbonded interactions with a charge of zero and van der Waals parameters $\sigma = 1.7 \text{ \AA}$ and $\epsilon = 0.12 \text{ kcal/mol}$, as parametrized in the CHARMM36 force field³⁴ and the bound O_2 in its ground electronic state ($^3\Sigma_g^-$) for which accurate MRCISD+Q calculations are available.³⁵ These calculations employed the cc-pCVQZ basis set and the 12 electrons in the last 8 orbitals, including core-valence and relativistic contributions from the lower electronic states, were correlated.³⁵ The energies are represented using a reproducing kernel Hilbert space (RKHS) approach^{36,37} or they were fitted to a Morse potential $V(r) = D_e (1 - e^{-\beta(r-r_e)})^2$. The parameters from a least-squares fit are $D_e = 123.1 \text{ kcal/mol}$, $r_{\text{eq}} = 1.2075 \text{ \AA}$, and $\beta = 2.68673 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ for the well depth, equilibrium separation and steepness parameters, respectively. For the simulations using a RKHS representation the MRMD module in CHARMM was suitably modified.

For water two models are considered in the present work. One is the standard transferable interaction potential 3 points (TIP3P) water model³¹ which is rigid. In order to study energy transfer between the highly excited oxygen molecule and the internal water degrees of freedom a flexible water model, a modified Kumagai, Kawamura and Yokokawa (KKY) model was used as well.^{32,33} This model has also been used for studies of ASW in the past.^{3,33}

The functional form of the KKY model involves a stretching term

$$E_{\text{str}} = D_e (1 - e^{-\beta(r-r_{\text{eq}})}) - D_e \quad (4)$$

with $D_e = 75.037$ kcal/mol, $r_{\text{eq}} = 0.957$ Å, and $\beta = 2.74$ Å⁻¹. The bending potential is

$$E_{\text{bend}} = 2f_k \sqrt{k_1 k_2} \sin^2(\theta - \theta_{eq}) \quad (5)$$

with

$$k_i = \frac{1}{e^{g_r(r_i-r_m)} + 1} \quad (6)$$

where $\theta_{eq} = 99.50^\circ$ and $k_i = \frac{1}{e^{g_r(r_i-r_m)} + 1}$, r_i is one of the O-H bond distances and $g_r = 6.99$ Å⁻¹ and $r_m = 1.402$ Å are original force field parameters and $f_k = 0.11$ J⁻¹ is a reparametrized bending parameter, fitted to match the experimental bending frequency (see Table S1).³³

The ASW is prepared by annealing liquid water from 300 K to 50 K⁴ for a total simulation time of 10 ns. The final density (1.01 g/cm³) of the system is compatible with what is expected for high density amorphous solid water.³⁸ To study O₂ formation within ASW, a cavity with volume ~ 1000 Å³ is created by removing 15 water molecules. Then, the system is minimized and equilibrated and further relaxed by running a 1 ns equilibrium simulation at 50 K. This leads to one main cavity with a volume of 583 Å³ and several smaller cavities with volumes ranging from 30 to 100 Å³. The cavity volumes were determined from GHE-COM.³⁹ No further deformation is observed after this preparation.

3 Results

In the following, the results are discussed separately for formation of O_2 in an inside ASW-cavity and for recombination at the surface.

3.1 Recombination in the cavity

Initial conditions for O_2 -formation were generated from a 500 ps equilibrium MD simulation at 50 K with the two oxygen atoms in the same internal cavity as illustrated in Figure 2. From this simulation, 1000 structures were chosen to initiate MS-ARMD simulations. The initial distribution of oxygen-oxygen separations (see Figure 3) has distinct maxima at 3.4 Å, 7.0 Å, and 10.0 Å covering a wide range of initial conditions. The oxygen atoms are almost thermalized, with a kinetic temperature of 70 K compared with 50 K of the surrounding water lattice, although the meaning of temperature for a diatomic molecule is somewhat debatable.

All 1000 rebinding simulations are run for 100 ps and 16 of them are extended out to 5 ns to better characterize the relaxation process. The fraction of O_2 -forming simulations is 79.3 % within 100 ps with half of them forming O_2 within 20 ps. The whole range of initial separations (between 3.4 Å and ~ 13 Å) leads to formation of O_2 , see red distribution in Figure 3. Typical O_2 -formation curves (black, red, blue, indigo) are reported in Figure 4 whereas for the green trace no molecular oxygen is formed on the 100 ps time scale. The red trace shows that O_2 can also be formed transiently (at 40 ps), break up, reform and stabilize at a later stage. The overall distribution of the O_2 -formation times is strongly peaked at short times with an extended tail, see top panel of Figure 4.

Figure 3: Initial distribution of the oxygen-oxygen separation $P(r)$ at the beginning of the rebinding simulations using [TIP3P/RKHS]. $P(r)$ has three maxima at ~ 3.4 Å (the minimum of the O–O van der Waals complex), at 7.0 Å and at 10.0 Å. The total distribution (black) is compared with the one for initial conditions that lead to rebinding (red, 793 events on the 100 ps time scale). The inset shows the time series for the oxygen–oxygen distance $r(t)$ for one sample trajectory and confirms that all distances in $P(r)$ can be sampled even for one single trajectory.

Figure 4: Top: Histogram $P(\tau)$ of the formation times for the 793 reactive simulations; 40% react within the first 20 ps and the cumulative fraction is shown as the red line. Several time series $r_{OO}(t)$ are shown in the inset. In black and indigo two examples of a reaction within the first 20 ps, a late reaction (around 40 ps, blue), and in green a simulation where dissociation occurs soon after O₂ recombination (red) and in green a simulation where the atoms remain in the unbound state. Bottom: interatomic distance (panel A), O₂ kinetic energy (panel B) and temperature profiles for water (red trace) and the overall system (black trace, panel C) for one recombination process. At $t = 23$ ps a nonproductive collision occurs and stabilization of O₂ starts after $t > 55$ ps. In panel B the right hand side y -axis reports the temperature associated with the kinetic energy of O₂.

Because rebinding of the two oxygen atoms leads to the liberation of the O_2 binding energy, it is expected that the kinetic temperature in the system increases. This is illustrated for one particular trajectory in Figure 4 bottom panel. The lower panel in Figure 4A reports the O_2 distance as a function of simulation time for one specific trajectory. At $t = 23$ ps a short encounter of the two oxygen atoms occurs which, however, does not stabilize O_2 . Only after 55 ps molecular O_2 forms. Concomitantly, the kinetic energy and the temperature increase significantly, as is shown in Figure 4B. This also leads to a marked temperature increase in the overall system from 50 K to > 60 K.

Due to the weak coupling between the O_2 stretch and the phonons of the solid water matrix, vibrational relaxation of the diatomic is slow. In order to quantify this, 16 trajectories using [TIP3P/RKHS] were continued out to ~ 5 ns, see Figure S2A. Relaxation times were estimated by fitting the time dependent oxygen-oxygen separation $r_{OO}(t)$ to a sum of exponentials

$$r_{OO}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^2 a_i \exp(-t/\tau_i) + r_0 \quad (7)$$

or to a stretched exponential

$$r_{OO}(t) = a \exp(-(t/\tau)^\beta) + r_0 \quad (8)$$

with $r_0 = 1.2075 \text{ \AA}$, which is the O_2 equilibrium separation. Using stretched exponentials is probably more meaningful in the present context as such a dependence has been found to be particularly suitable to describe the relaxation of glasses⁴⁰ and for ligand rebinding to proteins⁴¹ both of which are characterized by distributed barriers. In the present case (see Table 1) it is also found that the quality of the fit improves when one stretched exponential function is used compared to a fit to two exponentials. Considering one particular trajectory, the exponential decays involve a rapid decay $\tau_1 = 0.5$ ns and a longer relaxation $\tau_2 = 14.6$ ns whereas one stretched exponential leads to $\tau^{\text{SE}} = 1.4$ ns with $\beta = 0.21$. The average

long-time relaxation for the 16 trajectories is $\tau_2 = 15 \pm 0.5$ ns, see Figure S2A.

Table 1: Parameters and quality for fitting the O₂ vibrational relaxation to exponential (first line), one stretched exponential (second line) using Eqs. 7 and 8, respectively. The force fields (O₂ potential and water) with which the simulations were run are also indicated.

Region	FF	a_1 (Å)	a_2 (Å)	τ_1 (ns)	τ_2 (ns)	β	$RMSD$ (Å)
Inside	[TIP3P/RKHS]	0.28	0.38	0.5	14.6	-	3.638×10^{-3}
		1.38	-	1.4	-	0.207	6.546×10^{-5}
Surface	[TIP3P/RKHS]	0.35	0.31	1.1	83.4	-	9.154×10^{-3}
		1.08	-	1.1	-	0.144	2.032×10^{-4}
Surface	[KKY/RKHS]	0.27	0.34	0.7	20.7	-	2.156×10^{-3}
		1.12	-	0.9	-	0.182	3.082×10^{-4}
Surface	[TIP3P/Morse]	0.29	0.25	3.2	206.9	-	3.223×10^{-2}
		1.08	-	1.3	-	0.139	4.680×10^{-4}

Upon O₂ formation the binding energy released will be partially converted into heat and dissipates through the ASW. To quantify this, the averaged kinetic energy of all water molecules projected along the z -direction is averaged on a (x, y) -grid with voxels $1 \times 1 \times 30$ Å³ (i.e. a column of height 30 Å and (x, y) -base 1×1 Å²). The average kinetic energy of all water atoms in a single column is calculated, and averaged over 8 independent trajectories for times 10 ps before the recombination (at $t = 0$), i.e. for $-10 < t < 0$. Recombination was considered to have occurred for $r_{OO} < 2.5$ Å. The corresponding heat map is shown in Figure 5A. The low energy region (blue) in the center of the chart corresponds to the cavity region where fewer water molecules are located along the z -direction.

A similar heat map was generated for the time $0 < t < 10$ ps, i.e. after recombination, see Figure 5B and the difference map is shown in Figure 5C. Heating of the ASW molecules around the recombination region is found to occur in a range of ~ 8 Å on the 10 ps time scale. Furthermore, energy flow is anisotropic due to the amorphous nature of the water matrix. Figure 5D shows an ensemble average over 10 ps and 8 trajectories for a situation in which the two oxygen atoms are separated by an initial distance of 5 Å and are not allowed

Figure 5: Averaged temperature distribution in the (x, y) -plane averaged over 8 simulations using the RKHS PES and TIP3P water before (panel A: $-10 \leq t \leq 0$ ps) and after (panel B: $0 \leq t \leq 10$ ps) O_2 -formation. Here, $t = 0$ is defined as the instance along each of the trajectories for which $r_{OO} < 2.5$ Å for the first time and all time series are aligned with respect to this reference. The color scale reports the kinetic energy (in kcal/mol). The averaged position of the center of mass of O_2 is indicated by filled circles. The low-energy region in the center of the simulation box is due to the cavity which contain fewer water molecules along the z -axis that can contribute to the kinetic energy. Panel C shows the difference between panels A and B which highlights the direction and magnitude of energy transfer. The region "a", delimited by the continuous line ellipse, represents the region where the recombination takes places, while the second region "b" is a qualitative delimitation of the energy flow after the reaction. Panel D shows the energy distribution for two not reacting oxygen atoms.

to recombine, i.e. MS-ARMD was disabled and the two oxygen atoms only interact through van der Waals interactions. The distribution of the kinetic energy in Figures 5A and D are comparable and differ substantially from panel B.

3.2 O₂ formation: Surface Reaction

Atomic oxygen recombination on the surface of ASW is probably even more relevant under astrophysical conditions. There are two typical scenarios: the Langmuir-Hinshelwood (LH)^{42,43} mechanism whereby the two reacting species are in thermal equilibrium with the environment before they react or the Eley-Rideal (ER)⁴⁴ mechanism for which a thermalized, surface-adsorbed reactant collides with an impinging, non-thermalized partner. The scenario explored here is the LH mechanism.

For these simulations, one of the oxygen atoms is initially localized (but unconstrained) in a surface cavity sufficiently deep to avoid spontaneous desorption for the present simulations and the second oxygen atom diffuses freely on the surface. Altogether, one 110 ns [Morse/TIP3], one 25 ns [KKY/RKHS], and one 10.5 ns [RKHS/TIP3] simulation were initially run and analyzed. The relaxation of the O–O bond length for the [Morse/TIP3] simulation is shown in Figures 6, S2 and S3. Relaxation is characterized by a rapid initial phase during which $\sim 50\%$ of the binding energy relax (relaxation to $v = 15$) within a few nanoseconds. This is followed by a second, considerably slower phase extending over many 10s to 100s of nanoseconds during which collisions with the surrounding water lattice can lead to de-excitation and re-excitation. Similarly, the [TIP3P/RKHS] simulation (see Figure S2) shows a first phase (with time constant $\tau_1^{\text{DE}} = 1.1$ ns from a double exponential (DE) fit) during which the average O–O distance decreases from $\langle r_{\text{OO}} \rangle = 2.1$ Å to 1.5 Å within 3.6 ns, followed by a much slower relaxation ($\tau_2^{\text{DE}} = 83.4$ ns) during which the O–O separation only decreases by another 0.1 Å. Using a single stretched exponential yields $\tau_1^{\text{SE}} = 1.1$ ns and

Figure 6: Time evolution of the O_2 vibrational relaxation and its fit to a stretched exponential function (Eq. 8) for a [TIP3P/Morse] simulation with recombination on the ASW surface. Scattering of the O_2 from the surrounding water lattice leads to the peaks in the relaxation curve. The right-hand y -axis label reports the vibrational quantum number from solving the 1d-Schrödinger equation using LEVEL.⁴⁵ After 110 ns of simulation time the O_2 molecule is still in a state corresponding to $v = 15$.

$\beta_1 = 0.144$, see Table 1 and for two stretched exponentials the parameters are $\beta_1 = 0.51$ for the short-time process ($\tau_2^{\text{SE}} = 0.9$ ns) and $\beta_2 = 0.02$ for the long-time process ($\tau_2^{\text{SE}} = 1.2$ ns). At the end of this simulation the water temperature has increased by ~ 15 K, see Figure 7.

Figure 7: The kinetic temperature of the O_2 (top panel) and the water (bottom panel, red) and the total system (green) after formation at $t = 0$ from a [TIP3P/RKHS] surface simulation. After 20 ns the average temperature of the system has increased by ~ 15 K. The spikes in the black trace are due to collisions of O_2 with the surrounding water matrix.

Simulations with the Morse Potential for the O-O coordinate and the TIP3P water model establishes that relaxation is slow. This model is computationally less demanding than the RKHS representation and longer simulations are possible. The relaxation times from the 110 ns simulation are $\tau_1 = 3.2$ ns and $\tau_2 = 207$ ns which can only be an estimate because the data from which this value was determined does not probe dynamics on this time scale. Nevertheless, these results confirm that coupling between the oxygen stretching mode and the water phonon modes is small.

To evaluate how water flexibility influences the relaxation dynamics of molecular oxygen, a 10.5 ns [KKY/RKHS] simulation was carried out. Such simulations are even more computational demanding because the KKY water is flexible and a time step of $\Delta t = 0.1$ fs is required in the MD simulation for energy conservation. Vibrational relaxation times decreases by a factor of two to four, with $\tau_1 = 0.7$ ns and $\tau_2 = 20.7$ ns for a double exponential fit. For the stretched exponential fits, the values of β increase by ~ 30 % compared to simulations with rigid waters (see Table 1) and the two relaxation times decrease to $\tau_1^{\text{SE}} = 0.5$ ns and $\tau_2^{\text{SE}} = 1.0$ ns. This suggests that the O_2 relaxation dynamics is somewhat less nonexponential probably due to coupling to the water matrix which also speeds up the relaxation process.

Stretched exponential decays have been employed in the past to discuss relaxation within a diffusion-trap model and to characterize the dynamics in disordered molecular systems.⁴⁶ The case $\beta = 1$ in Eq. 8 corresponds to a conventional exponential decay and for all other cases $0 < \beta < 1$. The value of β can be related to the effective dimensionality of the problem through $\beta = d^*/(d^* + 2)$ where $d^* = f \times d$, d is the dimensionality of the problem (here $d = 3$) and f is the fraction of active channels for relaxation.⁴⁶ Discussing the present results (see Table 1) for one stretched exponential, it is found that for surface relaxation $\beta \sim 0.15$ whereas for relaxation within the bulk $\beta \sim 0.2$. For relaxation in the bulk and $d = 3$ this yields $f = 1/6$ whereas for relaxation on the surface the value for d is not obvious *a priori*. For $d = 3$ the number of relaxation channels is $f = 0.12$ whereas for $d = 2$ the value increases to $f = 0.18$. It is reasonable to expect that more rapid relaxation is caused by a larger number of relaxation channels (i.e. a larger number of collision partners). Because $\tau^{\text{bulk}} > \tau^{\text{surface}}$ for [TIP3P/RKHS] one finds $d = 2$ for the relaxation on the surface.

In order to better characterize the formation probability for the surface reaction an additional 534 simulations, using [TIP3/RKHS], were performed. The two oxygen atoms were

Figure 8: Top: Time series of the O-O distance during 180 ps for eight different simulations, with one oxygen in a deep crevice: for three trajectories no recombination is observed, because the two atoms diffuse away from the cavity where the first atom is trapped; five reactions instead leads to the molecule formation. The colored arrows indicate the initial distance, r_{OO} , of the two atoms. In the central panel, the moving average of those last simulation is shown: as from the previous simulations, a slow relaxation of the O-O distance is observed. The bottom panel shows the maximum height of the ice surface, i.e. the maximum z -coordinate of any water molecule, compared with the z -coordinate of the center of mass of O_2 . The molecules remain, in all simulations, on the surface, regardless of whether they rebind or not.

placed in two neighboring cavities on the surface with an initial distance of 8 Å and velocities randomly chosen from a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution at $T = 50$ K. Within 25 ps, 25 % of the simulations lead to recombination with an average formation time of $\langle t_{\text{formation}} \rangle = 10.8$ ps, see Figure 8 This establishes that not only a specifically prepared initial state leads to O₂ formation but also initial conditions which require diffusion of the two oxygen atoms before recombination can take place.

3.3 Desorption of O₂

Despite energy in excess of 100 kcal/mol is available upon oxygen recombination, which compares with desorption energies of 2 to 3 kcal/mol,^{4,47} O₂ remains localized on the surface for the simulations described so far. In order to explicitly probe desorption, a set of 10 simulations, 50 ps each, is run with velocities from a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution at 50 K but with the z -component (perpendicular to the ASW surface) scaled according to

$$v_z = v_{z0}(1 + \lambda a) \tag{9}$$

with $\lambda \in [0..50]$ in increments of 1, and $a = 0.1$. With increasing λ the velocity orthogonal to the surface increases and desorption becomes more probable. For each value of λ the average probability for desorption was determined.

Figure 9: Probability for desorption from an average over 10 independent simulations with different z components perpendicular to the ASW surface. Black trace: simulations with rigid (TIP3P) water; red trace: simulations with the flexible KKY model. Desorption occurs for a vertical component of the kinetic energy of ~ 1.7 kcal/mol and for ~ 1.2 kcal/mol, for TIP3P and KKY, respectively. The process is illustrated in the schematic.

For a rigid water model, desorption is observed for an average perpendicular kinetic energy of 2.0 kcal/mol (see Figure 9 black curve). If desorption occurs it takes place within 0.5 ps. Similar results are obtained when using a flexible water model but the energy for desorption is reduced to 1.5 kcal/mol (see Figure 9) because the O_2 stretch can now couple to the water deformation modes. Such energies for desorption are consistent with those determined from laboratory experiments of 1.8 kcal/mol.⁴⁷

4 Discussion and Conclusion

In this work formation of molecular oxygen on cold ASW surfaces is examined both inside amorphous solid water and on its surface. Oxygen (^3P) migration in and on ASW has been found from simulations⁴ and in experiments using neon matrices.²¹ If two oxygen atoms $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ approach one another sufficiently closely the process is rapid as it is barrierless. Once O_2 has formed, relaxation of the highly excited molecule takes place on the 10 to 100 ns time scale with full relaxation requiring considerably longer, though, well beyond the current simulation times. The rate limiting step for vibrational relaxation is coupling to the water phonon modes. For O_2 recombination on ASW it is found that even the highly vibrationally excited molecule does usually not desorb which also occurs due to inefficient coupling of the O_2 stretch to the water-phonon modes. With a flexible water model the desorption energy decreases by 25 % compared to rigid water and vibrational energy relaxation speeds up by a factor of ~ 4 .

Experimentally, vibrational energy transfer has been found to be very inefficient for NO near the surface of an insulator. For $\text{NO}(v = 1)$ the survival probability of scattering from LiF is 70% to 100%, with error bars up to 100% at all energies.⁴⁸ More recently, high survival probabilities (small probabilities for vibrational relaxation) have also been found for $\text{NO}(v = 12)$ on LiF(001).⁴⁹ Similarly, the probability for vibrational excitation of NO scattered from diamond was found to be only 5×10^{-3} and the vibrational relaxation probability of $\text{CO}(v = 1)$ on LiF is of comparable magnitude (10^{-3}).⁵⁰ Finally, on NaCl(100), CO vibrational energy relaxation occurs on the ms time scale.⁵¹ Relaxation on insulators (mainly by phonons) is inefficient due to the large mismatch in the frequencies of the diatomic and the phonons which leads to small coupling between these degrees of freedom. Conversely, for a conductive solid, coupling of intramolecular vibrations with phonons and electron-hole pairs accelerates energy transfer such as for vibrational relaxation of CO on Cu(111) which occurs on the ps timescale.⁵²

Photolysis of adsorbed SO_2 onto ASW and recombination of $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$, which is the process considered here, leads exclusively to $\text{O}_2(^3\Sigma_g^-)$, predominantly in vibrationally excited states $v \leq 3$. The time of flight in these experiments is on the order of μs which agrees quite well with results from the present simulations. Extrapolating the stretched exponential decay from the [KKY/RKHS] simulations from recombination on the ASW surface (see Table 1) to $1 \mu\text{s}$ yields $r_{\text{OO}} = 1.2386 \text{ \AA}$ which corresponds to $v = 2$, consistent with experiment.¹⁷ Formation of electronically excited $\text{O}_2(^1\Delta_g$ and $^1\Sigma_g^+)$ has been found from $\text{OH} + \text{O}(^3\text{P})$ involving a barrierless and an activated process, respectively.¹⁷ The fraction of O_2 in its $^1\Delta_g$ state was 2.5 %.⁵³ Given that the $^3\Sigma_g^-$, $^1\Delta_g$, and $^1\Sigma_g^+$ of O_2 dissociate to the same asymptote ($\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}(^3\text{P})$) it will be interesting to include electronically excited states in future work. For these states PESs of similar quality are available.³⁵ The recombination dynamics can be treated with trajectory surface hopping (TSH)⁵⁴ including nonadiabatic transitions within the Landau-Zener^{55,56} formalism. This has recently been done using multidimensional RKHS PESs for the reactive dynamics of the [CNO]-system.⁵⁷

The long vibrational relaxation times (ns to $\sim \mu\text{s}$ or probably even longer) found here for O_2 on ASW are consistent with vibrational relaxation of a high-frequency diatomic on an insulating surface such as water. If the water molecules lack internal degrees of freedom (rigid, TIP3P) the relaxation times are longer by about a factor of 4 compared with simulations in which the water-bending mode is available for coupling (flexible, KKY). For more quantitative results on the vibrational relaxation times much longer MD simulations will be required, though.

The present findings suggest that diffusion of atomic species followed by collisions in and on ASW and subsequent vibrational relaxation can lead to stable molecules at low temperatures. This complements and is in agreement with laboratory experiments that find

generation of O₂ and O₃.^{2,13,14,17,21,58–60} Such a mechanism for O₂ formation may also be operative at conditions prevalent in the interstellar medium although there, alternative routes such as the reactive O+OH collision are considered to be important, too.^{16,17}

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